

Analytical Report

Sample data report

New Mexico Bureau of Geology
and Mineral Resources

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Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-01	Customer sample ID: ESS1	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	4070	uS/cm	1		3/19/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-01	Customer sample ID: ESS1	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.1	ph Units	1		3/18/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-01	Customer sample ID: ESS1	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	232	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	88.0	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Potassium	20.9	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Silicon	13.9	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Sodium	580	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Strontium	4.24	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-01	Customer sample ID: ESS1	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/17/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/17/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/17/2020
Barium	0.022	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	3/17/2020

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Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020
Boron 11	0.437	mg/L	10	0.005	(0.05)	3/17/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020
Copper 65	0.0059	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01	(0.1)	3/17/2020
Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020
Lithium	0.191	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/17/2020
Manganese	0.146	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/17/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.011	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/17/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/17/2020
Silicon	14.8	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	3/17/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020
Strontium	4.21	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/17/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/17/2020
Uranium	0.0114	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020
Zinc 66	0.0089	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-01	Customer sample ID: ESS1	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.69	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/16/2020
Chloride	817	mg/L	10	1 (10)	3/16/2020
Fluoride	1.91	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/16/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/16/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/16/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	3/16/2020
Sulfate	827	mg/L	10	1 (10)	3/16/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
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Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-01	Customer sample ID: ESS1	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	295	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	359	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-01	Customer sample ID: ESS1	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	46.25	meq/L	1		
Cations total	44.59	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-1.84	%	1		
SiO2	31.6	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2780	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-01	Customer sample ID: ESS1	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	942	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
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	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-02	Customer sample ID: ESS2	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	4100	uS/cm	1		3/19/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-02	Customer sample ID: ESS2	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	7.7	ph Units	1		3/18/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-02	Customer sample ID: ESS2	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	236	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/19/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	3/19/2020
Magnesium	88.9	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/19/2020
Potassium	21.7	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/19/2020
Silicon	12.2	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	3/19/2020
Sodium	575	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/19/2020
Strontium	4.33	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/19/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-02	Customer sample ID: ESS2	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/17/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/17/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/17/2020
Barium	0.023	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	3/17/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/17/2020
Boron 11	0.438	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	3/17/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/17/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/17/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/17/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/17/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	3/17/2020

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Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020
Lithium	0.191	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/17/2020
Manganese	0.075	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/17/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.011	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/17/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/17/2020
Silicon	12.8	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	3/17/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020
Strontium	4.22	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/17/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/17/2020
Uranium	0.0111	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-02	Customer sample ID: ESS2	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.69	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/16/2020
Chloride	824	mg/L	10	1 (10)	3/16/2020
Fluoride	1.88	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/16/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/16/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/16/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	3/16/2020
Sulfate	839	mg/L	10	1 (10)	3/16/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-02	Customer sample ID: ESS2	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	289	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	352	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020

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	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-02	Customer sample ID: ESS2	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	46.61	meq/L	1		
Cations total	44.69	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-2.10	%	1		
SiO2	27.4	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2800	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-02	Customer sample ID: ESS2	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	956	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
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Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-03	Customer sample ID: ESS3	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	4070	uS/cm	1		3/19/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-03	Customer sample ID: ESS3	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.3	ph Units	1		3/18/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-03	Customer sample ID: ESS3	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	231	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/19/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	3/19/2020
Magnesium	88.5	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/19/2020
Potassium	22.3	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/19/2020
Silicon	12.6	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	3/19/2020
Sodium	570	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/19/2020
Strontium	4.26	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/19/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-03	Customer sample ID: ESS3	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/17/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/17/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/17/2020
Barium	0.019	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	3/17/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/17/2020
Boron 11	0.457	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	3/17/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/17/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/17/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/17/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/17/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	3/17/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
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	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020
Lithium	0.196	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/17/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/17/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.012	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/17/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/17/2020
Silicon	13.6	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	3/17/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020
Strontium	4.24	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/17/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/17/2020
Uranium	0.0118	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020
Vanadium	0.0053	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-03	Customer sample ID: ESS3	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.74	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/16/2020
Chloride	818	mg/L	10	1 (10)	3/16/2020
Fluoride	1.87	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/16/2020
Nitrate	0.79	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/16/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/16/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	3/16/2020
Sulfate	841	mg/L	10	1 (10)	3/16/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-03	Customer sample ID: ESS3	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	261	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	318	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020

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	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-03	Customer sample ID: ESS3	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	45.92	meq/L	1		
Cations total	44.16	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-1.95	%	1		
SiO2	29.0	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2770	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-03	Customer sample ID: ESS3	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	940	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

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	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-04	Customer sample ID: ESS4	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	4100	uS/cm	1		3/19/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-04	Customer sample ID: ESS4	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.4	ph Units	1		3/18/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-04	Customer sample ID: ESS4	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	238	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/19/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	3/19/2020
Magnesium	90.5	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/19/2020
Potassium	23.7	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/19/2020
Silicon	13.4	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	3/19/2020
Sodium	588	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/19/2020
Strontium	4.41	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/19/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-04	Customer sample ID: ESS4	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/17/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/17/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/17/2020
Barium	0.019	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	3/17/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/17/2020
Boron 11	0.470	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	3/17/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/17/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/17/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/17/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/17/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	3/17/2020

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	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020
Lithium	0.197	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/17/2020
Manganese	0.017	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/17/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.013	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/17/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/17/2020
Silicon	14.2	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	3/17/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020
Strontium	4.28	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/17/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/17/2020
Uranium	0.0125	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-04	Customer sample ID: ESS4	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.60	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/16/2020
Chloride	817	mg/L	10	1 (10)	3/16/2020
Fluoride	1.93	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/16/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/16/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/16/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	3/16/2020
Sulfate	839	mg/L	10	1 (10)	3/16/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-04	Customer sample ID: ESS4	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	268	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	327	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020

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	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-04	Customer sample ID: ESS4	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	46.00	meq/L	1		
Cations total	45.50	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-0.54	%	1		
SiO2	30.4	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2800	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-04	Customer sample ID: ESS4	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	967	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-05	Customer sample ID: ESS5	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	4100	uS/cm	1		3/19/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-05	Customer sample ID: ESS5	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.1	ph Units	1		3/18/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-05	Customer sample ID: ESS5	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	234	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/19/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	3/19/2020
Magnesium	87.5	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/19/2020
Potassium	22.3	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/19/2020
Silicon	12.1	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	3/19/2020
Sodium	566	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/19/2020
Strontium	4.26	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/19/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-05	Customer sample ID: ESS5	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/17/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/17/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/17/2020
Barium	0.018	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	3/17/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/17/2020
Boron 11	0.477	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	3/17/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/17/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/17/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/17/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/17/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	3/17/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020
Lithium	0.197	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/17/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/17/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.013	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/17/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/17/2020
Silicon	13.3	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	3/17/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020
Strontium	4.30	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/17/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/17/2020
Uranium	0.0121	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020
Vanadium	0.0057	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/17/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-05	Customer sample ID: ESS5	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.72	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/16/2020
Chloride	817	mg/L	10	1 (10)	3/16/2020
Fluoride	1.82	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/16/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/16/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/16/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	3/16/2020
Sulfate	841	mg/L	10	1 (10)	3/16/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-05	Customer sample ID: ESS5	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	271	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	331	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-05	Customer sample ID: ESS5	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	46.08	meq/L	1		
Cations total	44.09	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-2.21	%	1		
SiO2	28.4	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2770	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-05	Customer sample ID: ESS5	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	945	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-06	Customer sample ID: ESS6	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	4150	uS/cm	1		3/19/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-06	Customer sample ID: ESS6	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.2	ph Units	1		3/18/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-06	Customer sample ID: ESS6	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	240	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/19/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	3/19/2020
Magnesium	88.8	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/19/2020
Potassium	23.1	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/19/2020
Silicon	12.1	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	3/19/2020
Sodium	568	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/19/2020
Strontium	4.29	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/19/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-06	Customer sample ID: ESS6	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/18/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/18/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/18/2020
Barium	0.018	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	3/18/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/18/2020
Boron 11	0.487	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	3/18/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/18/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/18/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/18/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/18/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	3/18/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/18/2020
Lithium	0.192	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/18/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/18/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.015	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/18/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/18/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/18/2020
Silicon	13.1	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	3/18/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/18/2020
Strontium	4.32	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/18/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/18/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/18/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/18/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/18/2020
Uranium	0.0133	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/18/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/18/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/18/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-06	Customer sample ID: ESS6	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.74	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/16/2020
Chloride	829	mg/L	10	1 (10)	3/16/2020
Fluoride	1.71	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/16/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/16/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/16/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	3/16/2020
Sulfate	859	mg/L	10	1 (10)	3/16/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-06	Customer sample ID: ESS6	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	279	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	341	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-06	Customer sample ID: ESS6	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	46.97	meq/L	1		
Cations total	44.55	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-2.64	%	1		
SiO2	28.1	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2810	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-06	Customer sample ID: ESS6	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	964	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-07	Customer sample ID: SS1	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	1770	uS/cm	1		3/19/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-07	Customer sample ID: SS1	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.5	ph Units	1		3/18/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-07	Customer sample ID: SS1	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	103	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	3/19/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	5	0.02 (0.1)	3/19/2020
Magnesium	37.6	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	3/19/2020
Potassium	13.2	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	3/19/2020
Silicon	10.6	mg/L	5	0.01 (0.05)	3/19/2020
Sodium	238	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	3/19/2020
Strontium	1.86	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/19/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-07	Customer sample ID: SS1	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Barium	0.036	mg/L	5	0.001 (0.005)	3/18/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Boron 11	0.208	mg/L	5	0.005 (0.025)	3/18/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	5	0.01 (0.05)	3/18/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Lithium	0.082	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	3/18/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	3/18/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.011	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	3/18/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	3/18/2020
Silicon	11.3	mg/L	5	0.02	(0.1)	3/18/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Strontium	1.81	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	3/18/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	3/18/2020
Uranium	0.0035	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Zinc 66	0.0031	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-07	Customer sample ID: SS1	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.16	mg/L	1	0.1	3/16/2020
Chloride	250	mg/L	5	1 (5)	3/16/2020
Fluoride	1.51	mg/L	1	0.1	3/16/2020
Nitrate	0.14	mg NO3/L	1	0.1	3/16/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	1	0.1	3/16/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	1	0.5	3/16/2020
Sulfate	300	mg/L	5	1 (5)	3/16/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-07	Customer sample ID: SS1	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	277	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	332	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-07	Customer sample ID: SS1	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	18.93	meq/L	1		
Cations total	18.95	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	0.05	%	1		
SiO2	24.2	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	1140	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-07	Customer sample ID: SS1	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	413	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-08	Customer sample ID: SS2	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	1790	uS/cm	1		3/19/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-08	Customer sample ID: SS2	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.2	ph Units	1		3/18/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-08	Customer sample ID: SS2	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	110	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	3/19/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	5	0.02 (0.1)	3/19/2020
Magnesium	39.6	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	3/19/2020
Potassium	13.9	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	3/19/2020
Silicon	11.4	mg/L	5	0.01 (0.05)	3/19/2020
Sodium	246	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	3/19/2020
Strontium	1.95	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/19/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-08	Customer sample ID: SS2	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Barium	0.037	mg/L	5	0.001 (0.005)	3/18/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Boron 11	0.205	mg/L	5	0.005 (0.025)	3/18/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Copper 65	0.0033	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	5	0.01 (0.05)	3/18/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Lithium	0.083	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	3/18/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	3/18/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.011	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	3/18/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	3/18/2020
Silicon	11.9	mg/L	5	0.02	(0.1)	3/18/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Strontium	1.83	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	3/18/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	3/18/2020
Uranium	0.0036	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-08	Customer sample ID: SS2	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.17	mg/L	1	0.1	3/16/2020
Chloride	253	mg/L	5	1 (5)	3/16/2020
Fluoride	1.51	mg/L	1	0.1	3/16/2020
Nitrate	0.16	mg NO3/L	1	0.1	3/16/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	1	0.1	3/16/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	1	0.5	3/16/2020
Sulfate	301	mg/L	5	1 (5)	3/16/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-08	Customer sample ID: SS2	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	277	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	338	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-08	Customer sample ID: SS2	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	19.01	meq/L	1		
Cations total	19.84	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	2.13	%	1		
SiO2	25.5	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	1160	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-08	Customer sample ID: SS2	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	439	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-09	Customer sample ID: SS3	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	1800	uS/cm	1		3/19/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-09	Customer sample ID: SS3	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.1	ph Units	1		3/18/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-09	Customer sample ID: SS3	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	107	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	3/19/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	5	0.02 (0.1)	3/19/2020
Magnesium	38.6	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	3/19/2020
Potassium	13.5	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	3/19/2020
Silicon	11.2	mg/L	5	0.01 (0.05)	3/19/2020
Sodium	239	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	3/19/2020
Strontium	1.90	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/19/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-09	Customer sample ID: SS3	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Barium	0.035	mg/L	5	0.001 (0.005)	3/18/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Boron 11	0.205	mg/L	5	0.005 (0.025)	3/18/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	5	0.01 (0.05)	3/18/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Lithium	0.085	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	3/18/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	3/18/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.011	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	3/18/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	3/18/2020
Silicon	11.7	mg/L	5	0.02	(0.1)	3/18/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Strontium	1.85	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	3/18/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	3/18/2020
Uranium	0.0035	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-09	Customer sample ID: SS3	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.17	mg/L	1	0.1	3/16/2020
Chloride	258	mg/L	5	1 (5)	3/16/2020
Fluoride	1.45	mg/L	1	0.1	3/16/2020
Nitrate	0.20	mg NO3/L	1	0.1	3/16/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	1	0.1	3/16/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	1	0.5	3/16/2020
Sulfate	306	mg/L	5	1 (5)	3/16/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-09	Customer sample ID: SS3	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	276	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	337	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-09	Customer sample ID: SS3	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	19.26	meq/L	1		
Cations total	19.26	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-0.01	%	1		
SiO2	25.1	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	1160	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-09	Customer sample ID: SS3	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	425	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-10	Customer sample ID: SS4	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	1840	uS/cm	1		3/19/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-10	Customer sample ID: SS4	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.4	ph Units	1		3/18/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-10	Customer sample ID: SS4	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	106	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	3/19/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	5	0.02 (0.1)	3/19/2020
Magnesium	39.2	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	3/19/2020
Potassium	13.6	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	3/19/2020
Silicon	11.3	mg/L	5	0.01 (0.05)	3/19/2020
Sodium	244	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	3/19/2020
Strontium	1.93	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/19/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-10	Customer sample ID: SS4	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Barium	0.030	mg/L	5	0.001 (0.005)	3/18/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Boron 11	0.211	mg/L	5	0.005 (0.025)	3/18/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Copper 65	0.0028	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	5	0.01 (0.05)	3/18/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Lithium	0.085	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	3/18/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	3/18/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.011	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	3/18/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	3/18/2020
Silicon	12.0	mg/L	5	0.02	(0.1)	3/18/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Strontium	1.87	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	3/18/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	3/18/2020
Uranium	0.0036	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-10	Customer sample ID: SS4	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.16	mg/L	1	0.1	3/16/2020
Chloride	269	mg/L	5	1 (5)	3/16/2020
Fluoride	1.44	mg/L	1	0.1	3/16/2020
Nitrate	0.17	mg NO3/L	1	0.1	3/16/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	1	0.1	3/16/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	1	0.5	3/16/2020
Sulfate	317	mg/L	5	1 (5)	3/16/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-10	Customer sample ID: SS4	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	269	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	322	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-10	Customer sample ID: SS4	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	19.65	meq/L	1		
Cations total	19.46	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-0.49	%	1		
SiO2	25.7	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	1180	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-10	Customer sample ID: SS4	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	426	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-11	Customer sample ID: SS5	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	1870	uS/cm	1		3/19/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-11	Customer sample ID: SS5	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.5	ph Units	1		3/18/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-11	Customer sample ID: SS5	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	108	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	3/19/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	5	0.02 (0.1)	3/19/2020
Magnesium	40.0	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	3/19/2020
Potassium	13.9	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	3/19/2020
Silicon	11.3	mg/L	5	0.01 (0.05)	3/19/2020
Sodium	244	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	3/19/2020
Strontium	1.96	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/19/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-11	Customer sample ID: SS5	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Barium	0.031	mg/L	5	0.001 (0.005)	3/18/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Boron 11	0.211	mg/L	5	0.005 (0.025)	3/18/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Copper 65	0.0036	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	5	0.01 (0.05)	3/18/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Lithium	0.088	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	3/18/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	3/18/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.011	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	3/18/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	3/18/2020
Silicon	11.8	mg/L	5	0.02	(0.1)	3/18/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Strontium	1.95	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	3/18/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	3/18/2020
Uranium	0.0038	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Zinc 66	0.0033	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-11	Customer sample ID: SS5	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.15	mg/L	1	0.1	3/17/2020
Chloride	276	mg/L	5	1 (5)	3/17/2020
Fluoride	1.45	mg/L	1	0.1	3/17/2020
Nitrate	0.19	mg NO3/L	1	0.1	3/17/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	1	0.1	3/17/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	1	0.5	3/17/2020
Sulfate	324	mg/L	5	1 (5)	3/17/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-11	Customer sample ID: SS5	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	277	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	329	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-11	Customer sample ID: SS5	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	20.15	meq/L	1		
Cations total	19.69	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-1.16	%	1		
SiO2	25.2	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	1200	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-11	Customer sample ID: SS5	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	435	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-12	Customer sample ID: SS6	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	1910	uS/cm	1		3/19/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-12	Customer sample ID: SS6	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.3	ph Units	1		3/18/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-12	Customer sample ID: SS6	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	118	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	3/19/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	5	0.02 (0.1)	3/19/2020
Magnesium	42.7	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	3/19/2020
Potassium	14.6	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	3/19/2020
Silicon	11.2	mg/L	5	0.01 (0.05)	3/19/2020
Sodium	260	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	3/19/2020
Strontium	2.13	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/19/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-12	Customer sample ID: SS6	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Barium	0.030	mg/L	5	0.001 (0.005)	3/18/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Boron 11	0.213	mg/L	5	0.005 (0.025)	3/18/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Copper 65	0.0038	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	3/18/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	5	0.01 (0.05)	3/18/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Lithium	0.090	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	3/18/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	3/18/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.011	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	3/18/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	3/18/2020
Silicon	11.6	mg/L	5	0.02	(0.1)	3/18/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Strontium	2.01	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	3/18/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	3/18/2020
Uranium	0.0039	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020
Zinc 66	0.0056	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	3/18/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-12	Customer sample ID: SS6	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.17	mg/L	1	0.1	3/17/2020
Chloride	284	mg/L	5	1 (5)	3/17/2020
Fluoride	1.40	mg/L	1	0.1	3/17/2020
Nitrate	0.14	mg NO3/L	1	0.1	3/17/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	1	0.1	3/17/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	1	0.5	3/17/2020
Sulfate	329	mg/L	5	1 (5)	3/17/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-12	Customer sample ID: SS6	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	277	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	338	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-12	Customer sample ID: SS6	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	20.47	meq/L	1		
Cations total	21.10	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	1.52	%	1		
SiO2	24.8	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	1250	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-12	Customer sample ID: SS6	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	471	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-13	Customer sample ID: GS-1	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3210	uS/cm	1		3/17/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-13	Customer sample ID: GS-1	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.3	ph Units	1		3/18/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-13	Customer sample ID: GS-1	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	173	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/26/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	3/26/2020
Magnesium	78.3	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/26/2020
Potassium	18.8	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/26/2020
Silicon	8.51	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	3/26/2020
Sodium	433	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/26/2020
Strontium	3.44	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/26/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-13	Customer sample ID: GS-1	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Barium	0.019	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	3/25/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Boron 11	0.377	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	3/25/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	3/25/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Lithium	0.162	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Silicon	9.51	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	3/25/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Strontium	3.45	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Uranium	0.0054	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Zinc 66	0.0129	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-13	Customer sample ID: GS-1	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/30/2020
Chloride	642	mg/L	10	1 (10)	3/30/2020
Fluoride	1.68	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/30/2020
Nitrate	0.88	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/30/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/30/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	3/30/2020
Sulfate	656	mg/L	10	1 (10)	3/30/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-13	Customer sample ID: GS-1	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	228	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	278	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-13	Customer sample ID: GS-1	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.44	meq/L	1		
Cations total	34.42	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-2.85	%	1		
SiO2	20.3	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2170	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-13	Customer sample ID: GS-1	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	755	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-14	Customer sample ID: GS-2	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3240	uS/cm	1		3/17/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-14	Customer sample ID: GS-2	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.3	ph Units	1		3/18/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-14	Customer sample ID: GS-2	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	174	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/26/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	3/26/2020
Magnesium	77.9	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/26/2020
Potassium	18.5	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/26/2020
Silicon	8.54	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	3/26/2020
Sodium	430	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/26/2020
Strontium	3.43	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/26/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-14	Customer sample ID: GS-2	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Barium	0.019	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	3/25/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Boron 11	0.379	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	3/25/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	3/25/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Lithium	0.160	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Silicon	9.32	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	3/25/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Strontium	3.45	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Uranium	0.0054	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Zinc 66	0.0110	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-14	Customer sample ID: GS-2	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/30/2020
Chloride	636	mg/L	10	1 (10)	3/30/2020
Fluoride	1.63	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/30/2020
Nitrate	0.96	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/30/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/30/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	3/30/2020
Sulfate	651	mg/L	10	1 (10)	3/30/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-14	Customer sample ID: GS-2	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	229	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	280	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-14	Customer sample ID: GS-2	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.22	meq/L	1		
Cations total	34.26	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-2.79	%	1		
SiO2	19.9	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2150	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-14	Customer sample ID: GS-2	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	755	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-15	Customer sample ID: GS-3	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3240	uS/cm	1		3/17/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-15	Customer sample ID: GS-3	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.3	ph Units	1		3/18/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-15	Customer sample ID: GS-3	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	171	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	78.5	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Potassium	18.8	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Silicon	9.00	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Sodium	446	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Strontium	3.46	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-15	Customer sample ID: GS-3	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Barium	0.019	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	3/25/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Boron 11	0.378	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	3/25/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	3/25/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Lithium	0.157	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Silicon	9.38	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	3/25/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Strontium	3.43	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Uranium	0.0054	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Zinc 66	0.0128	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-15	Customer sample ID: GS-3	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/30/2020
Chloride	643	mg/L	10	1 (10)	3/30/2020
Fluoride	1.63	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/30/2020
Nitrate	0.55	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/30/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/30/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	3/30/2020
Sulfate	660	mg/L	10	1 (10)	3/30/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-15	Customer sample ID: GS-3	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	227	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	259	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	9	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-15	Customer sample ID: GS-3	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.55	meq/L	1		
Cations total	34.89	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-2.33	%	1		
SiO2	20.1	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2180	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-15	Customer sample ID: GS-3	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	751	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-16	Customer sample ID: GS-4	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3230	uS/cm	1		3/17/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-16	Customer sample ID: GS-4	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.3	ph Units	1		3/18/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-16	Customer sample ID: GS-4	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	174	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/26/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	3/26/2020
Magnesium	78.8	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/26/2020
Potassium	18.8	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/26/2020
Silicon	8.57	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	3/26/2020
Sodium	431	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/26/2020
Strontium	3.43	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/26/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-16	Customer sample ID: GS-4	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Barium	0.019	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	3/25/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Boron 11	0.377	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	3/25/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	3/25/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Lithium	0.161	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Silicon	9.23	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	3/25/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Strontium	3.40	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Uranium	0.0054	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Zinc 66	0.0120	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-16	Customer sample ID: GS-4	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/30/2020
Chloride	638	mg/L	10	1 (10)	3/30/2020
Fluoride	1.62	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/30/2020
Nitrate	0.64	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/30/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/30/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	3/30/2020
Sulfate	653	mg/L	10	1 (10)	3/30/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-16	Customer sample ID: GS-4	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	222	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	269	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-16	Customer sample ID: GS-4	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.15	meq/L	1		
Cations total	34.40	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-2.49	%	1		
SiO2	19.7	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2160	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-16	Customer sample ID: GS-4	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	758	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-17	Customer sample ID: GS-5	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3240	uS/cm	1		3/17/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-17	Customer sample ID: GS-5	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.4	ph Units	1		3/18/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-17	Customer sample ID: GS-5	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	172	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/26/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	3/26/2020
Magnesium	77.6	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/26/2020
Potassium	18.5	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/26/2020
Silicon	8.52	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	3/26/2020
Sodium	428	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/26/2020
Strontium	3.40	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/26/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-17	Customer sample ID: GS-5	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Barium	0.019	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	3/25/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Boron 11	0.375	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	3/25/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	3/25/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Lithium	0.162	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Molybdenum 95	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Silicon	9.22	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	3/25/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Strontium	3.42	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Uranium	0.0053	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Zinc 66	0.0084	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-17	Customer sample ID: GS-5	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.52	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/30/2020
Chloride	638	mg/L	10	1 (10)	3/30/2020
Fluoride	1.66	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/30/2020
Nitrate	0.52	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/30/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/30/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	3/30/2020
Sulfate	655	mg/L	10	1 (10)	3/30/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-17	Customer sample ID: GS-5	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	222	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	266	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-17	Customer sample ID: GS-5	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.18	meq/L	1		
Cations total	34.07	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-3.01	%	1		
SiO2	19.7	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2150	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-17	Customer sample ID: GS-5	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	750	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-18	Customer sample ID: GS-6	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3240	uS/cm	1		3/17/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-18	Customer sample ID: GS-6	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.2	ph Units	1		3/18/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-18	Customer sample ID: GS-6	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	173	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/26/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	3/26/2020
Magnesium	77.6	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/26/2020
Potassium	18.4	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/26/2020
Silicon	8.50	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	3/26/2020
Sodium	428	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/26/2020
Strontium	3.41	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/26/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-18	Customer sample ID: GS-6	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Barium	0.019	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	3/25/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Boron 11	0.378	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	3/25/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	3/25/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Lithium	0.158	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Silicon	9.43	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	3/25/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Strontium	3.43	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Uranium	0.0054	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Zinc 66	0.0127	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-18	Customer sample ID: GS-6	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/30/2020
Chloride	633	mg/L	10	1 (10)	3/30/2020
Fluoride	1.66	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/30/2020
Nitrate	0.98	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/30/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/30/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	3/30/2020
Sulfate	651	mg/L	10	1 (10)	3/30/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-18	Customer sample ID: GS-6	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	226	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	275	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-18	Customer sample ID: GS-6	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.07	meq/L	1		
Cations total	34.09	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-2.83	%	1		
SiO2	20.2	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2150	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-18	Customer sample ID: GS-6	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	750	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-19	Customer sample ID: SSS1	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3270	uS/cm	1		3/17/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-19	Customer sample ID: SSS1	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.2	ph Units	1		3/18/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-19	Customer sample ID: SSS1	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	180	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/26/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	3/26/2020
Magnesium	80.1	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/26/2020
Potassium	19.2	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/26/2020
Silicon	10.1	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	3/26/2020
Sodium	437	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/26/2020
Strontium	3.48	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/26/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-19	Customer sample ID: SSS1	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Barium	0.020	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	3/25/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Boron 11	0.375	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	3/25/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	3/25/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Lithium	0.156	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Molybdenum 95	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Nickel	0.0057	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Silicon	10.7	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	3/25/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Strontium	3.43	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Uranium	0.0056	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Zinc 66	0.0136	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-19	Customer sample ID: SSS1	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.70	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/30/2020
Chloride	642	mg/L	10	1 (10)	3/30/2020
Fluoride	1.61	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/30/2020
Nitrate	0.72	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/30/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/30/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	3/30/2020
Sulfate	661	mg/L	10	1 (10)	3/30/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-19	Customer sample ID: SSS1	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	231	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	282	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-19	Customer sample ID: SSS1	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.62	meq/L	1		
Cations total	35.06	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-2.17	%	1		
SiO2	22.9	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2190	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-19	Customer sample ID: SSS1	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	779	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-20	Customer sample ID: SSS2	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3260	uS/cm	1		3/17/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-20	Customer sample ID: SSS2	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.3	ph Units	1		3/18/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-20	Customer sample ID: SSS2	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	173	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	77.8	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Potassium	18.8	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Silicon	10.3	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Sodium	441	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Strontium	3.40	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-20	Customer sample ID: SSS2	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Barium	0.020	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	3/25/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Boron 11	0.375	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	3/25/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	3/25/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Lithium	0.155	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Nickel	0.0069	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Silicon	10.6	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	3/25/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Strontium	3.43	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Uranium	0.0056	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Zinc 66	0.0095	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-20	Customer sample ID: SSS2	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/30/2020
Chloride	640	mg/L	10	1 (10)	3/30/2020
Fluoride	1.50	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/30/2020
Nitrate	0.79	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/30/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/30/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	3/30/2020
Sulfate	659	mg/L	10	1 (10)	3/30/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-20	Customer sample ID: SSS2	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	232	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	283	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-20	Customer sample ID: SSS2	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.52	meq/L	1		
Cations total	34.70	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-2.55	%	1		
SiO2	22.6	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2180	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-20	Customer sample ID: SSS2	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	753	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-21	Customer sample ID: SSS3	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3260	uS/cm	1		3/17/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-21	Customer sample ID: SSS3	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.2	ph Units	1		3/18/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-21	Customer sample ID: SSS3	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	178	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/26/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	3/26/2020
Magnesium	79.2	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/26/2020
Potassium	18.9	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/26/2020
Silicon	9.79	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	3/26/2020
Sodium	431	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/26/2020
Strontium	3.43	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/26/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-21	Customer sample ID: SSS3	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Barium	0.022	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	3/25/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Boron 11	0.386	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	3/25/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	3/25/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Lithium	0.157	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Nickel	0.0096	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Silicon	10.9	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	3/25/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Strontium	3.42	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Uranium	0.0058	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Zinc 66	0.0128	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-21	Customer sample ID: SSS3	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/31/2020
Chloride	640	mg/L	10	1 (10)	3/31/2020
Fluoride	1.54	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/31/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/31/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/31/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	3/31/2020
Sulfate	657	mg/L	10	1 (10)	3/31/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-21	Customer sample ID: SSS3	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	231	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	282	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-21	Customer sample ID: SSS3	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.48	meq/L	1		
Cations total	34.63	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-2.60	%	1		
SiO2	23.3	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2180	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-21	Customer sample ID: SSS3	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	770	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-22	Customer sample ID: SSS4	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3280	uS/cm	1		3/17/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-22	Customer sample ID: SSS4	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.2	ph Units	1		3/18/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-22	Customer sample ID: SSS4	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	176	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/26/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	3/26/2020
Magnesium	78.9	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/26/2020
Potassium	18.8	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/26/2020
Silicon	9.83	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	3/26/2020
Sodium	435	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/26/2020
Strontium	3.46	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/26/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-22	Customer sample ID: SSS4	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Barium	0.020	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	3/25/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Boron 11	0.383	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	3/25/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	3/25/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Lithium	0.157	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Nickel	0.0060	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Silicon	10.9	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	3/25/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Strontium	3.43	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Uranium	0.0057	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Zinc 66	0.0089	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-22	Customer sample ID: SSS4	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/31/2020
Chloride	639	mg/L	10	1 (10)	3/31/2020
Fluoride	1.82	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/31/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/31/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/31/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	3/31/2020
Sulfate	656	mg/L	10	1 (10)	3/31/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-22	Customer sample ID: SSS4	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	228	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	279	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-22	Customer sample ID: SSS4	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.36	meq/L	1		
Cations total	34.70	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-2.33	%	1		
SiO2	23.3	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2170	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-22	Customer sample ID: SSS4	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	764	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-23	Customer sample ID: SSS5	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3260	uS/cm	1		3/17/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-23	Customer sample ID: SSS5	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.3	ph Units	1		3/18/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-23	Customer sample ID: SSS5	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	178	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/26/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	3/26/2020
Magnesium	79.1	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/26/2020
Potassium	18.9	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/26/2020
Silicon	9.99	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	3/26/2020
Sodium	442	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/26/2020
Strontium	3.50	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/26/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-23	Customer sample ID: SSS5	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Barium	0.020	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	3/25/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Boron 11	0.380	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	3/25/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	3/25/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Lithium	0.165	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Silicon	10.7	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	3/25/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Strontium	3.48	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Uranium	0.0058	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Zinc 66	0.0103	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-23	Customer sample ID: SSS5	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/31/2020
Chloride	638	mg/L	10	1 (10)	3/31/2020
Fluoride	1.63	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/31/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/31/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/31/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	3/31/2020
Sulfate	656	mg/L	10	1 (10)	3/31/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-23	Customer sample ID: SSS5	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	231	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	282	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-23	Customer sample ID: SSS5	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.40	meq/L	1		
Cations total	35.11	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-1.81	%	1		
SiO2	23.0	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2180	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-23	Customer sample ID: SSS5	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	770	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-24	Customer sample ID: SSS6	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3270	uS/cm	1		3/17/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-24	Customer sample ID: SSS6	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.2	ph Units	1		3/18/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-24	Customer sample ID: SSS6	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	175	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/26/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	3/26/2020
Magnesium	78.3	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/26/2020
Potassium	18.7	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/26/2020
Silicon	9.76	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	3/26/2020
Sodium	428	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	3/26/2020
Strontium	3.39	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/26/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-24	Customer sample ID: SSS6	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Barium	0.020	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	3/25/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Boron 11	0.382	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	3/25/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	3/25/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	3/25/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Lithium	0.156	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Silicon	10.8	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	3/25/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Strontium	3.42	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	3/25/2020
Uranium	0.0058	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020
Zinc 66	0.0123	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	3/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-24	Customer sample ID: SSS6	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.53	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/31/2020
Chloride	636	mg/L	10	1 (10)	3/31/2020
Fluoride	1.55	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/31/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/31/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	3/31/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	3/31/2020
Sulfate	653	mg/L	10	1 (10)	3/31/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-24	Customer sample ID: SSS6	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	231	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	281	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/18/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200305
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/10/2020 6:03:59 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-24	Customer sample ID: SSS6	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.25	meq/L	1		
Cations total	34.29	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-2.78	%	1		
SiO2	23.0	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2160	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200305-24	Customer sample ID: SSS6	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	761	mg CaCO3/ L	1		